

An Empirical Study on Online Food Processing and Delivery Industry's Startups with Special Reference to Customer Satisfaction in Ajmer Region

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Abstract: The Food Processing and Food delivery Startups finding new ways to promote and deliver “TASTE” at the door step. There are many startups working in this very industry all over the world as well as in India also. These startups are both small and big few are lucky to are funding's from big giants operating in state capitals as well as in other cities also by expanding their working network.

This study is concentrating upon Ajmer which is of historical tourist importance, many of the players from the food processing and delivery industry are operating here, and the main focus is on the customer satisfaction upon delivery of food on many parameters like happiness index, mode of payment, what is being delivered, freshness etc.

Keywords: Food Processing, Online food delivery, Zomato, Swigg, Paytm, Amazon, Customer Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

There has been a huge boom in the number of food delivery startups in few last years. A food delivery company is referred to be the one which takes customer order on its online system supported through online website or through Mobile applications and transfers it to a food production unit/restaurant owned or in association with, followed by a delivery boy picking up the order from the restaurant and delivering it to the customer. Dominos and Pizza Hut are doing the same form a long time but there is a slight difference in them and others, others do not manufacture or process food they just deliver it.

Customers are getting benefits like home delivery, discount offers, reward points etc. the core proposition remains convenience both for startups and customers. The taste, quality etc. are not the concern of the online food delivery startups, they just deliver what is being ordered. People are getting used to it in small towns like Ajmer, there is a big opportunity for these startups as there is less competition in comparison to metro city in terms of area and other players.

The current study is focusing on the small city, Ajmer which has ample opportunities as it is having historical and tourist importance. A well-known place on the world map.

II. POPULAR ONLINE FOOD DELIVERY STARTUPS IN INDIA

1. FoodPanda

Fig. 1. Showing Foodpanda website image.
Source: www.foodpanda.in

Launched in March last year, Rocket Internet's FoodPanda has rapidly become one of the major players in India to look out for. The startup now serves customers in 12 cities in India with 2,000 restaurant choices. Being a typical Rocket Internet portfolio company, FoodPanda recently raised a whopping \$20 million to conquer the online food delivery service in eight Asian countries.

2. JustEat

Fig. 2. Showing JustEat website image.
Source: www.justeat.in

UK-based JustEat made its first move to the Indian market in 2011 by acquiring a majority stake in local startup HungryZone. Now JustEat delivers food from over 2,500 restaurants in India's three cities of Mumbai, Bangalore, and Delhi-NCR. The company also handles online table bookings.

JustEat comes prepared with a buckload of money too. Last year the startup raised \$64 million in series C funding. JustEat partners with local lifestyle search engine Burpp for its online food ordering feature.

Fig. 3. Showing Burpp website image.

Source: www.burpp.com

3. TastyKhana

Fig. 4. Showing TastyKhana website image.

Source: www.tastykhana.in

Started as early as 2007, TastyKhana now connects users to 3,000 restaurants located in seven cities in India. The startup is backed by European-based online food delivery company DeliveryHero, which has presence in 14 countries, with early seed as well as series A round.

This cooperation with DeliveryHero has so far proven effective as TastyKhana records 400 percent in order volume growth since establishing the partnership.

4. DeliveryChef

Fig. 5. Showing DeliveryChef website image.

Source: www.deliverychef.in

Run by two female founders, Ankita Tandon and Aditi Talreja, DeliveryChef started delivering dishes to customers in late 2010. Today DeliveryChef is present in seven Indian cities with over 500 restaurants in its system.

5. BigBite

Fig. 6. Showing BigBite website image.

Source: www.bigbite.in

BigBite seems to be consolidating its restaurant network in one city, which is Delhi-NCR. The company planned to grab as many as 2,000 restaurants from that city alone by the end of 2012, in last August the 10-men team was still at 600 restaurant mark. Today BigBite caters to a total of five cities in India.

6. Titbit

Fig. 7. Showing Titbit website image.

Source: www.titbit.com

Founded in 2011, not only does Titbit deliver food from more than 400 local restaurants in Mumbai and Pune, but the startup also offers other services which has an international reach. One of Titbit's biggest products is its iPad powered digital menu ordering platform which is being used by numerous restaurants in the US, UK, Turkey, Singapore, and India.

Last year Titbit acquired food ordering service Foodkamood to strengthen its presence in the industry. [1]

III. FOOD DELIVERY / PROCESSING INDUSTRY OPERATING IN AJMER

There are many operators working in this sector like one

- Who are manufacturing and delivering food at door step
- Who are manufacturing and delivering food at Train
- Do not manufacture but delivering Food at door step

First we discuss about, who are manufacturing and delivering food at door step - the major stakeholders are Pizza Hut and Dominos, they are in the industry from long time and serving the customers all over the world. They are having their presence in Ajmer too.

Fig. 8. Showing PizzaHut website image.

Source: <https://online.pizzahut.co.in/home>

The above fig. shows there is 50% off on delivery of pizza on using a particular code while ordering. At Ajmer location, the pizza hut has its presence but they are not delivering themselves at the door step, they have take-away counter.

Fig. 9. Showing PizzaHut website image.

Source: <https://online.pizzahut.co.in/home>

Pizza Hut, normally delivering its order at home or office at other states but they have not started their services at Ajmer, May being near future they will start doing so.

While Dominos, at Ajmer is providing home delivery services for online or on call orders, they have sitting place for pizza lovers to eat.

Fig. 10. Showing Dominos website image.

Source: <https://www.dominos.co.in/store-location/Ajmera>

Dominos, has its old and trusted promise delivery in 30 min. still working in Ajmer also. Dominos has its mobile app, from where anyone can order their favorite pizza.

Fig. 15. Showing website image of railyatri providing food on Train.
Source: <https://www.railyatri.in/buy-food-in-train>

Fig. 16. Showing website image of travelkhana providing food on Train.
Source: <https://www.travelkhana.com/>

Fig. 17. Showing website image of travelerfood providing food on Train.
Source: http://www.travelerfood.com/food_delivery-at-ajmer-jn-railway-station-aii.php

Train No.	Train Name	Train Status	Arr. Time	Dep. Time
02264	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	08:45	01:40
02265	BRADWELL TO AJMER JN	AT AJMER JN (AJMER JN)	08:50	08:10
02266	BRADWELL TO AJMER JN	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	09:10	07:20
02267	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT AJMER JN (AJMER JN)	10:30	End
02268	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	09:45	01:10
02269	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT AJMER JN (AJMER JN)	10:45	02:10
02270	BRADWELL TO AJMER JN	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	11:30	01:40
02271	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT AJMER JN (AJMER JN)	11:35	01:40
02272	BRADWELL TO AJMER JN	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	12:20	01:40
02273	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT AJMER JN (AJMER JN)	12:25	01:40
02274	BRADWELL TO AJMER JN	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	13:10	01:40
02275	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT AJMER JN (AJMER JN)	13:15	01:40
02276	BRADWELL TO AJMER JN	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	14:00	01:40
02277	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT AJMER JN (AJMER JN)	14:05	01:40
02278	BRADWELL TO AJMER JN	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	14:50	01:40
02279	AJMER JN TO BRADWELL	AT AJMER JN (AJMER JN)	14:55	01:40
02280	BRADWELL TO AJMER JN	AT BRADWELL (BRADWELL)	15:40	01:40

Fig. 18. Showing website image of travelzaika providing food on Train.
Source: http://www.travelzaika.com/food_delivery.php?stationid=AIJ

Fig. 19. Showing website image of travelzaika providing link to pay online through PayUMoney
Source: <https://www.payumoney.com/paybypayumoney/#/A8760AE26A3479161B5C09CBCFB295CA>

There are many vendors who are catering online food train orders many are having mobile apps to get the orders and make sure it reaches to the concern person. Many of them give “COD- cash on delivery” and online payment option through “PayuMoney”. This gives user flexibility to pay while ordering the desired food on train. Here also the extensive use of mobile and internet gives vendors a new opportunity to take a share in the billion dollar business.

On the other hand, Indian Railways are also providing food in train, but the quality of food and services are in competition with these new players. Indian Railways are constantly upgrading their food services due to this upcoming competition.

The other section - **Do not manufacture but delivering Food at door step**, this section give ample opportunity to new startups and they are making an impact and getting funding from many major funding agencies. There is a big list of new and established players but due to the geographical constraint “Ajmer” for the research paper the author is concentrating upon the food delivery services playing in “Ajmer” only.

Fig. 20. Showing website image of Zomato providing food app.
Source: <https://www.zomato.com/ajmer>

Fig. 21. Showing website image of swiggy providing food items.
Source: <https://www.swiggy.com/ajmer/restaurants>

Fig. 22. Showing website image of foodpanda providing food items. Source: <https://www.foodpanda.in>

Fig. 23. Showing website image of Dominos and PizzaHut. Source: website of Dominos and PizzaHut

In the following sequence other than the Pizza Hut and other players the companies like Paytm and Amazon who are not in the direct business of delivering cooked and packed food at the door step are also in the picture by offering discount coupons and cashback on using their payment services like Paytm.

Paytm on its application there is a section food delivery and when you open the section it asks you for your location and according to your location there is a list of restaurants who are connected to the Paytm network, by the time the research work was conducted Paytm has **98 restaurants** of Ajmer in its network.

Each restaurants are offering some additional discount on the purchase like 10% or 20% on ordering through Paytm. Now a days people are using Paytm services for many utilities like recharging Mobile – prepaid or postpaid mobile payment, their landline phone bills, petrol pump for fuel, at shops in the

market etc., they are having additional services for paying ordered food and having discount and cashbacks.

Fig. 24. Showing Paytm app image of providing food items. Source: Paytm app interface.

Fig. 25. Showing Paytm app image of providing food items in Ajmer it is associated with 98 restaurants in Ajmer. Source: Paytm app interface

Fig. 26. Showing Paytm app image of providing food delivery and Restaurant deals in Ajmer Source: Paytm app interface

Other than Paytm, Amazon is in the similar pattern to offer flat 30 rupees off or 30% off etc. on its Amazon app, they are offering different offers on different food providers like on swiggy flat 30 rupees off on order applicable on 3 times and on Dominos 30% back up to 75 rupees valid till some date. Other than Swiggy and Dominos Amazon is providing these offers to other service providers such as Box8, Fassos, FreshMenu, and Mojo etc. who are not having their presence at Ajmer market.

Paytm and Amazon who are not into direct delivery or into this business they are also having their presence this reflects that there is a scope of business for those also who not directly related to the current discussed business are.

By having intervention of these big players people are having more offers and discounts on ordering the food online, people who are serving the Ajmer foodies are getting ample amount of business to cater, side by side the Paytm like organizations are having increased in loyal customers who are having discounts and benefits.

Fig. 27. Showing Amazon app image of providing food items in Ajmer it is associated with various food delivery companies in Ajmer.

Source: Amazon app interface

Fig. 28. Showing Amazon app image of providing food items in Ajmer it is associated with various food delivery companies in Ajmer.

Source: Amazon app interface

Other than these offer providers, food delivery Services Company has its own apps through which customer can order the food articles.

Their apps are also having various offers like, GOODFOODTRAIL, HDFC5X, ORDER50, APAYMARCH etc. these above mention offers are from the Swiggy's app which offers different discount offers through various banks, occasions, seasons etc. people when use these codes like ORDER50 they will have 50% discount on the ordered food article, if they use APAYMARCH for e.g. They will have 100% cashback etc. these are the marketing strategies used by the companies to attract business and there is a good level of competition in between these companies to attract and hold the customers, as the food suppliers are limited in the market and

the food delivery services options are increasing and in near future some more players will enter in the market.

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- ◆ Bonus Reward Points would be posted after 90 days of campaign end date. 1X points would be posted d...
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- ◆ Offer not valid on Domino's outlets
- ◆ Other T&Cs may apply
- ◆ Offer valid till Mar 31, 2019 23:59 PM

OK, GOT IT

← OFFERS

RESTAURANT OFFERS PAYMENT OFFERS/ COUPONS

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Get 15% discount using RBL Bank Credit Card
Use code RBL200 & get 15% discount upto Rs. 200 on your order above Rs. 300. Offer valid only on Saturdays and Sundays.

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- ◆ Other T&Cs may apply
- ◆ Offer valid till 31st March 2019

OK, GOT IT

← OFFERS

RESTAURANT OFFERS PAYMENT OFFERS/ COUPONS

 RBL200

Get 15% discount using RBL Bank Credit Card
Use code RBL200 & get 15% discount upto Rs. 200 on your order above Rs. 300. Offer valid only on Saturdays and Sundays.

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Get flat Rs.30 cashback on orders above Rs.99 for 10 orders. No code required.

 Get Rs.50 cashback using Axis
Get Rs.50 cashback on 3 months Super membership using Axis Bank Card

- ◆ Valid on 3-months Swiggy Super membership
- ◆ Other T&Cs may apply
- ◆ Offer valid until 15th April 2019

OK, GOT IT

- ◆ Valid on orders above Rs.99
- ◆ Valid on your first 10 transactions using Amazon Pay during the offer period
- ◆ Cashback will be credited into your Amazon Pay account within 3 working days
- ◆ Offer not valid on Domino's outlets
- ◆ Other T&Cs may apply
- ◆ Offer valid till 12th May 2019

Fig. 29. Showing Swiggy app image of providing food items in Ajmer showing various discount offers from various providers. Source: Swiggy app interface

With these kinds of offers, people are tend to purchase or order food online and through apps, they are having on door delivery and discounts and other benefits like suggesting their apps to their friend circle will give them some reward or discount, to experience the business span the cab giant Ola has also entered into the food business through its division Foodpanda.

There is a survey by RedSeer Consulting, on the points like trusted brand, best value and experience they have ranked swiggy on the top followed by Zomato.

A RedSeer Consulting survey for the October-December period has ranked Swiggy No.1 with a total score of 96, followed by Zomato with 82 points, Uber Eats 73 and Ola's Foodpanda 70.

Online food ordering and delivery startup Swiggy, run by Bundl Technologies Pvt. Ltd, emerged on top in trust and customer satisfaction in a food-tech survey by research firm RedSeer Management Consulting Pvt. Ltd. According to the latest edition of the RedSeer FoodTech Leadership Index (FLI), Swiggy ranked no. 1 with a total score of 96, outscoring arch-rival Zomato (Zomato Media Pvt. Ltd), which came in second with a score of 82 in the fourth quarter of 2018.[3]

Fig. 30. Showing image of survey conducted by RedSeer for food providing companies [Not in Ajmer] Source: https://www.livemint.com

The above mentioned survey and the results includes some participants like UberEats, Foodpanda etc. who are not present in Ajmer till date of research study done by the author .

To find out the presence of online food delivery companies/ startups in AJMER he author designer a series of questionnaire to understand the market and to gain insight of customer satisfaction.

As these companies are getting funding in millions of dollar to get hold in new and promising market. It is required to estimate the value given back by these companies to be customers of Ajmer.

As it is quite predictable that the online food delivery business/ sector is promising and in near future many new food restaurants will open and population of Ajmer will increase so as the food delivery providers will also increase in that scenario this study will act as a benchmark for the further research. As customer is the king in the market only those companies will survive in this diversified customer based

market who is customer favorite or from those services customer is satisfied.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF QUESTIONNAIRE

In this section the author is going to analyze the responses from various respondents who have taken this survey and give their valuable suggestions to make this survey as a benchmark for further studies.

Let us begin with the survey question analysis and interpretation to find out the satisfaction of Ajmer customer towards the various online food delivery companies/ startups.

1. Please choose appropriate age group from the given option

This question deals with the age group of respondents, the maximum respondents who has taken the survey are from the age group of 20 -25 years, following by 26- 30 years and followed by 36 and above its 2% of the respondents.

This result gives the picture that most of the young generation is actively participating in the ordering of online food from various restaurants through these various food delivery service providers.

Nowadays, youngster are having mobile with internet connectivity and other facilities there are ample chances to use these facilities for own purpose or under peer pressure. The next segment of age group is 26-30 yrs. Who are may be into service are catering these services to save time and effort.

2. Kindly choose your profession/ occupation from the given options

Moving to the next question regarding the profession of respondents, majority of the respondents are from the group of students 66%, followed by working professional with 21%

later on home maker and businessman, this gives the clear picture that students are making this possible for the companies who are operating in this sector followed by the working professionals and followed by home makers who may be place the order due to the demand of the children again who may be the students of some college or school.

3. How many of these online food manufacturing/ delivering companies / startups are serving at Ajmer

This question gives the exact image of scenario of Ajmer who are making their presence on the map of Ajmer in the food delivery business.

With 92% Zomato followed by Swiggy, and then pizza Hut and Dominos with 63% and 54 % respectively then comes the Paytm and Amazon in the chart.

This chart depicts the presence of Zomato in the market of Ajmer, it has created its presence and became number one in the survey list, the next player is Swiggy in the list and so on, and this gives the reflection of the market share absorbed by the Zomato in Ajmer, peoples first choice is Zomato to order the food online with delivery from zomato, it has its own benefits like discounts and other befits but zomato has come Numero Uno in Ajmer.

4. How many times you ordered online food in a month - approximately

This particular question deals with the number of orders placed by the customer for online food delivery services in a month, people are used to order 1-2 times in a months with 46% and followed by 3-4 times in a month with 45 %. This gives us a picture that people are ordering food articles through the apps or website to get delivered through the food delivery services. The customers, majorly giving the orders to get benefits offered by the corresponding apps owners of to seek initial

discount offers to give orders as the India is very price sensitive place and people are very reactive to the price variations and discount seekers, their loyalty moves with the discount offers, the repetitive orders is may be due to the reason to cash the discount offer made by the service provider.

5. According to you, Who motivates/ initiates to order online food in your family in gernal

This question deals with the motivating force who initiates the order the food through online services and get it delivered through the food delivery services. The respondents are mostly youngsters and they are having the facility of having mobile with internet connection get the maximum part of the pie followed by the children and followed by the friends or peer pressure.

This gives the picture of driving force who is making the impact in getting the order of the online food delivery.

6. According to you, are you satisfied by the timing of delivery means always on time to deliver your order?

This question deals with the timely delivery of ordered food article, this is important in terms of customer satisfaction as the expectation initiate and keeps on increasing after the ordering and countdown starts the app of service provider also helps in this situation to test the patience of customer by showing estimated time and real time location of delivery boy on the city map with continuous updating of the state.

If the delivery boy doesn't deliver the ordered item within the estimated time the taste and flavor also disturbed of food article and the temper of customer also lost. In this reference this question is its own importance, 87% of the respondents are saying Yes that the food item is delivered within the stipulated time and 12% are saying No, in the current situation majority of customers are satisfied with the delivery timing. 12% customer having some issues that could be resolved by talking to the customers and having their feedback to improve the service timing in near future.

7. According to you, the food delivered by the online services is similar in taste to that food ordered on the table in a restaurant?

This is a comparative question for the food lovers to answer, most of the customer are familiar with the taste and quality of the listed restaurants and have personally visited to eat. 84% are saying that the taste is similar to the food that has been ordered on table and ordered online. 15 % are not having the similar views there could be some issues in delivering like time and there could be some issues with restaurants in preparing the food for online delivery items, these could be resolved by having proper feedback from customer end.

8. According to you, when you get the delivery of the ordered food item it is still warm/ hot, when delivered? As it has to be.

This question could be the trailing question for question no 6, the freshness and temperature of the ordered food item is directly related to the timely delivery of the food item. If the food is still warm/ hot then it is assumed that it is being delivered in time. 83% of respondents are saying Yes to the question and 16.93% are not in support with the question.

The next question is related to the initiation of food items to be ordered online, the driving force behind the ordering online.

9. According to you, what impulses you to order food online through website/ mobile app.?

The home delivery feature with 83.07% is most liked by the customer and it became first driving force followed by 50.76% discount offers and with 30.76% family demand became third motivating force, convenience, coupons and reference bonus are following these major factors.

Home delivery feature that cannot be denied that attracts Indian customer mostly while ordering food items online through apps. Discount offers are motivating the persons who is actually paying for the ordered food, it is well known fact that Indian customers are discount seekers and this urge had become second prominent factor for this business, family demand is on the third place family has all kind of members young and old mostly younger ones are more demanding and this is the motivating factor for ordering the food article online.

10. According to you, there has been an increase in orders and competition in online food industry due to mobile apps.

This question deals with the increasing order and competition in the business, some prominent players are already in the market and other players are planning to enter the marketplace, if we look at the India's metro city's situation there are many service providers and there is a scope for more in near future as due to geographical distribution of these cities each and every service providers practically cannot cater the needs of all the city demands.

In case of Ajmer city, although the geographical distribution of land is not much but due to the Holy Dargaha Shariff and nearby Pushkar many tourist are coming to the city and population of Ajmer is increasing day by day and the restaurants are keep opening in that case there will be competition for fast delivery and accuracy of ordered food items.

There is an increase in order of food items other than the ordered on the table. The most probable reasons for that can be reflected from the question no. 9, Home delivery, Discount offers and family demand they are also in the support of increase in the orders from online apps for the restaurants.

11. According to you, where do you like to prefer your online food order to be delivered?

This question is again making home delivery as prominent factor for the success of online food delivery business. 89.23% of the respondents are willing to get their placed ordered to be delivered at home. 10.76% of the customers are making the choice at work place this small chunk of respondents are may be those persons who are ordering randomly or having different working conditions.

Home delivery is became an unbeatable factor in this business.

12. According to you, are you ready to pay the delivery charges on ordered online food through website or mobile app.?

This question is in the regard of "Delivery Charges" that is taken by the food delivery company like Swiggy or Zomato, this is the major revenue source for these companies, success of these kind of companies in this business is depending upon the number of orders in a day, with the strong competition in the field and other factors it is difficult to meet out the target.

66.61% of respondents are ready to pay the delivery charges incurred by these companies. They are taking small amount of charge like 20 -30 rupees on each orders but when if you

calculate the total amount in a day it became huge amount till the end of the month, but there is a catch in the situation the salary and other expenses for delivering the food items in the city.

35.38% are not ready to pay the charges, as the Indian customer mindset to save money, paying charges is ok when there is a suitable distance between the restaurant and home, if the distance is small and customer feels that the delivery charges are a bit high than expected.

The bottom line is this what is important your time or money.

13. According to you, do you want to avail schemes provided by online food delivery providers to waive off the delivery fee while ordering food online?

This question deals with the various schemes offered by food delivery companies through their apps to waive off the delivery charges, 92.30% are ready to opt the offer and not willing to pay the delivery charges, this gives an opposite reaction for above question where the respondents are ready to pay the delivery charges.

This is a typical example of Indian customer mindset, where people are conservative and try to save the money, companies are making this point as strategic move by offering some schemes if customer opt for schemes they are likely to bind with the service provider for some other offerings and if not the customer is paying the delivery charges.

The company is at a win-win situation in both the conditions.

14. According to you, where do you rate the performance of online food delivery services on Happiness Index?

This question is asking the respondents about the happiness index in respect of performance of online food delivery services.

16.92% are highly satisfied and 70.76% are satisfied the major chunk of the pie is full with the satisfied customer on happiness index, they are happy with the services provided by online food delivery companies

10.76% are at neutral stage like neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, this is the area where the companies should put their focus, and these are the customer which can be converted into satisfied customers the rest 1.5% customers who are highly dissatisfied well they are gone and cannot be retain back, from the pie chart it is very small amount if we compare the other part of the pie and few customers may be at this state but it is important to keep this area at its minimum level and try to remove this area from the pie. This is the area can increase due to several factors like quality of food and delivery timings etc.

15. According to you, which one of the following(s) online food services provider/ delivery provider is / are your favorite?

This question ask the respondents about their favorite food delivery provider with 76.46% zomato is on the top followed by 69.22% is Swiggy and on the third place is Dominos with 44.66% and with 21.53% it is Paytm. The results are indicating the app and service provider who is not in the direct business of food delivery services and it is marking its place on the chart. This may be due to the offering and payment mode offered by the Paytm, other food delivery services are not having the payment mode like Paytm. Sometimes these service providers charge extra other than delivery charges due to shortage of the delivery / courier services.

Zomato and Swiggy are at the top due to its delivery force that is always on the move to deliver the food items ordered online by customers.

16. According to you, in general what would you like to order when you are ordering online food through website or mobile apps?

This question asks the respondents about what they would like to order when it time to order online food. From the list of available choice like Vegetarian, Non – vegetarian, Shakes, Sweet, Thali, Main course, Rice, Meals, Pizza, Burger etc.

People at Ajmer mostly like to order vegetarian food with 85.71% of respondents are in support of this followed by pizza lovers with 71.42% then comes the meals and rice choices, non-vegetarian choice is supported by 19.04% people.

The choices reflects that most of the ordered food is highly influenced by youngsters due to the choices of Pizza and Burger.

17. According to you, how many times did you give feedback on online order through mobile app, email or website

This is one of the important question in the survey, the feedback from the customers people order food online due to many influencing factors like home delivery, discounts etc. but when they are satisfied or dissatisfied they do not react and doesn't react and do not give any feedback to the service provider.

The service provider feels that everything is alright but actually it is not and the services goes on as they are going creating more dissatisfying customers in the market eventually it is very late to cover the situation resulting into the loss of the market share.

In the current survey, 40.62% of the respondent do not share their views by giving proper feedback, 48.43% of respondents are giving their feedback "Sometimes" in that case whether it is good or bad experience the permutation / combination is depending on the customer and the experience. 4.68% gives

their feedback every time and 6.25% are giving their feedback randomly, this is again a situation where company feels that everything is going good.

Feedback is never considered important by the customer and mostly never taken seriously by the companies due to increase in competition or expanding the business.

The question where the survey had asked the customers to tell about satisfaction there are few customers who are not satisfied and probably these are those customers who never reacted and just dropped the service provider.

Proper feedback is the key to success and to convert neutral and dissatisfied customer into the satisfied customer, if taken seriously.

18. According to you, do you feel that prices of food listed in the menu of online food providers are fair if compared to the prices on table menu at restaurants?

This questions deals with the prices of the food items listed in the menu of online apps and the menu of restaurant at table. 25.39% of the respondents feels that there is a difference in the prices, 22.22% of customer doesn't find any difference and the major chunk of the pie, 46.03% never noticed or never tried to compare and 6.34% are saying that they should reconsider the pricing of online apps.

The major customer do not bother consider to see and compare the prices while ordering this may be due to various driving factor like discount factors, time constraints, family demand etc.

19. According to you, how do you rate the behavior of delivery boy when he is coming to deliver the ordered food at your preferred location like home/ work/ palace.

This a simple but once again an important question of the survey, the behavior of delivery boy while delivering the food articles the customer is meeting the delivery boy it is not as that simple, the customer is dealing with the company's representative his behavior may alter the future decision making of the customer.

According to the pie chart most of the people are satisfied with 36.06% and fair with 22.95%, moderate with 27.65% only 13.65% people rated the behavior as good, by giving the training how to deal with customer or something like that any orientation program which helps in dealing and understanding the customer and converting each and every customer into satisfied customer will generate more revenue and market share in near future. According to the survey result there is a scope in converting fair and moderate responded customer into good response customer. Feedback and other thing like repetitive orders

20. According to you, how do you rate the after sales services of online food services providers like in technical helping, tracking your order, cancellation of order, refund, wrong delivery of order etc.?

This question deals with the after sales service provided by online food delivery service, this is again became one of the important question of survey, after sales services, like delivery of food article, movement of delivery boy on the app, payment mode, errors and rectification and helping the customer into smooth buying experience. The major area of concern are like refund, wrong order delivered, delay in delivery, cancellation of order, first time user experience.

49.20% had rated as moderate followed by 31.74% as satisfied, 14.28% stated that as fair and 4.76% customer rated as good.

Looking at the percentage of the respondents the technical and other help provided or offered by the companies through app or call center people are a little satisfied followed by fair and major chunk of pie is rated with moderate response followed by satisfied response.

Still the totally satisfied customer sector of the pie chart is low, this is again could be the alarm for the future business improving condition and beating the competition.

21. According to you, would you like to continue placing order with - choose from the following online service provider(s)

This question deals with the placing order or repeating order with the specific service provider, the respondents had chosen zomato followed by swiggy, after that here comes the selection of pizza lovers, pizza hut and dominos and late on Paytm and Amazon.

Paytm and Amazon have marked their presence in the business where they are not directly involved in delivering food articles, yet they are in the selection list of the people and have increased competition.

These apps are not in the business directly for now but in near future they can be into this business like Foodpanda is subsidiary of OLA.

22. According to you, which of the following you would like to recommend to your family or friends?

This questions result also reflects the same output of choices like earlier one, Zomato and Swiggy are favorite of respondents with the presence of Paytm and Amazon in the mindset of people.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

To conclude the study after a long and elaborated analysis of the questionnaire the author can see the upcoming business sector in Ajmer online food delivery services. Many prominent players are already in the business and in near future there will be more as this sector has become profitable sector in which the service providers doesn't need to have restaurant and there is no need of customers directly, they are doing in-between job of delivering the food item from the manufacturer to the customer home.

Discount offer, coupons, convenience, home delivery are the key factors in the success of the players in this business, according to the survey there are many areas where there is a scope of improvement like feedback and after sales services etc.

This study also gives the researcher to explore more details like how many people are actually discount seekers, how many of them are actually buying the food online just because of home delivery option. The current study is restricted to the customer satisfaction and other factors, deep study on each factor can be done in near future.

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